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Interplay of Cell Configuration and Performance in Flow Field-Free Alkaline Electrolyser: Optimization of porous Transport Layer and Interlayers

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Abstract

Herein the impact of porous transport layer (PTL) structure, interlayer design and materials, and operating conditions on the performance and durability of anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers (AEMWEs) is thoroughly investigated. By using nickel felt PTLs with 250 μm and 450 μm thicknesses, and interlayers such as Ni mesh, Inconel 600, wire-sintered stainless steel (W-S SS), and wire-sintered nickel (W-S Ni), we systematically examined how mechanical compression affect membrane electrode assembly at low and high current densities. Electrochemical analyses demonstrated that the AEMWE cell assembled with the 450 μm Ni felt maintains its performance under high external pressures (10–20 bar), while nickel felt 250 μm performance deteriorate at high current density (e.g $> 1.5 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). Secondary interlayers significantly improved the initial performance by reducing interfacial contact resistance. However, long-term stability diverged among materials where W-S SS and Inconel suffered from degradation and increased resistance over time, likely due to oxidative passivation in the anode compartment of the AEMWE single cell. On the contrary, when W-S Ni is used as interlayer superior initial performance will maintain and degradation rate of just $0.18 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ over 160 hours at $0.5 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in 1 M KOH at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is observed. Postmortem inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) analysis revealed undetectable Ni leaching and moderate Fe dissolution from OER catalyst, i.e. NiFeO_x , in the anode compartment. These findings demonstrate the critical role of tailored interlayer and PTL configurations to achieve high-performance and stable AEM water electrolyzer operation under pressurized conditions and high current densities.

Figure 1. Graphical abstract illustrating the general schematic of the electrolyzer components and electrochemical characterization

Introduction

AEMWEs technology utilizes a solid polymer membrane electrolyte and a zero-gap configuration (i.e. OER and HER catalyst layers are pressed on both side of a membrane) and benefits from the alkaline environment, mostly KOH, which allows the use of less expensive platinum group metal (PGM)-free catalysts and stack materials, e.g nickel, potentially lowering capital costs compared to proton exchange membrane counterparts. Despite this advantage, AEMWE technology is still in its premature stage of development and lags behind commercial needs in terms of both performance and durability [1].

1 Scientific Approach

PTL properties, such as structure, materials, porosity etc. is have significant impact on water electrolyzers performance [2]. The structure of the PTL, like pore size and porosity, is crucial to facilitate mass transport, in both gas and liquid phases, and also can influence catalyst layer adhesion and contact resistance [3]. Compression of porous materials is often necessary to enhance electrical conductivity, while excessive compression can be problematic due to impeding mass transfer caused by reducing porosity [4].

Furthermore, crucial importance of flow field patterns, typically machined into end plates, have been extensively studied through theoretical modeling [5] and experimental analyses [6]. However, a flow field-free design is often preferred for simpler assembly and lower machining costs. Interlayers, i.e. additional components placed between the catalyst-coated substrate and the end plates, have been shown to significantly improve water electrolyzer performance [7] and resolve the need of flow fields. Additionally using these interlayers reduce localized mechanical stresses that can lead to membrane and catalyst layer delamination or cracking by uniform distribution of the externally applied clamping and/or piston pressure over the catalyst layer [1].

This study focuses on the interplay between cell configurations and electrochemical performance and durability of a flow field-free AEMWE in real world operating conditions.

2 Experiments

MEA and cell assembly

MEAs were prepared using in-house synthesized NiFeO_x (OER catalyst) and commercial Pt/C (HER catalyst) (40% Pt on carbon black, HiSPEC 4000, Alfa Aesar). Catalyst inks were sonicated in ethanol and sprayed onto Ni felt (250 or 450 μm, Bekaert) or carbon paper (Sigracet 39BC). MEAs were assembled by cold-pressing under external pressure of 10 or 20 bar where PTFE gaskets and EPDM O-rings sealed the water electrolyzer single cell.

Electrochemical testing

Single cells (with active area ca. 7.1 cm²) were tested with 0.1 or 1 M KOH fed to the anode at 2 mL·min⁻¹·cm⁻². electrochemical preconditioning of the MEA involved 0.05 A·cm⁻² for 1 h, then 3.5 A·cm⁻² for ca. 16 h. Performance was evaluated via polarization curves, EIS (10 kHz–0.1 Hz), and long-term chronopotentiometry at 0.5 or 1 A·cm⁻². Due to booster limitations, frequencies above 10 kHz could not be applied.

Post-mortem analysis

Electrolyte after stability tests (ca. 300 h) was analyzed by ICP-OES (ThermoFisher Scientific). Samples were acidified with HNO₃ and compared to blank KOH. Metal ion concentrations were quantified using calibration standards.

3 Results

Modulating pressure distribution via interlayer selection

To enhance the uniformity of the external applied pressure over MEA in a flow field-free AEM water electrolyzer, various interlayers were tested using pressure-sensitive films. Ni mesh alone configuration led to a non-uniform pressure distribution pattern with localized hotspots, risking mechanical degradation and uneven current distribution, fig. 2a-b. Adding a low-porosity materials e.g. wire-sintered stainless steel (W-S SS) or Inconel between Ni mesh and the MEA, see fig.1, significantly improved pressure homogeneity as is shown in fig.2c-d.

Figure 2. a) visual photograph showing (right side) the marks caused by Ni mesh on Ni PTL and its pressure distribution pattern on pressure sensitive film (left side). b) An optical microscopy image depicting the Ni PTL after being compressed at 10 bar within the cell assembly. Effect of including additional interlayer i.e., c) W-S SS on Ni felt (photo was taken using a digital camera) and d) Inconel on the pressure sensitive film. Inconel and W-S SS were placed between Ni mesh and PTL (i.e. Ni felt 450 μm).

Impact of porous transport layer (PTL) thickness on electrolyzer performance

Porous transport layer (PTL) thickness also influenced performance. MEAs with 450 μm thick Ni felt outperformed 250 μm under external applied pressure of 10 and 20 bar. Thinner PTLs suffered from mass transport limitations and pore collapse at higher applied pressures, while thicker one preserved porosity and contact quality. EIS analyses confirmed lower ohmic resistance for the 450 μm PTL due to better compression accommodation.

Interlayer design and material selection

Interlayer impacted both BoT performance and durability of an AEMWE. Adding Inconel, fig. 3a, or W-S SS, fig. 3b, improved initial performance compared to Ni mesh alone, fig. 3c, but durability diverged. Inconel degraded quickly, after ca. 30 h, due to the formation of a passive oxide layer, increasing both ohmic and charge transfer resistance. W-S SS was more stable but showed increased ohmic losses over time as well, fig. 3d-3f. Ultimately, W-S Ni was introduced to combine the benefits of mechanical support and chemical durability of the nickel in alkaline conditions and led to both superior initial performance and durability.

Figure 3. Effect of interlayer configuration on the performance of a flow-field-free water electrolyzer. Polarization curves and corresponding EIS spectra are shown for cell assemblies employing: (a and d) Ni mesh + Inconel, and (b and e) Ni mesh + wire-sintered stainless steel (W-S SS) and (c and f) Ni mesh only, as interlayers. EoT graphs represent cell performance after 30 hours operating at current density of 1 A.cm⁻². EIS analyses were carried out at applied potential of 1.8 V.

Long-term stability and Degradation Trends

Long-term testing with W-S Ni interlayers showed promising results: using 1 M KOH, at 0.5 A.cm⁻², led to a low degradation rate of 0.18 mV.h⁻¹. Performance at 1 A.cm⁻² showed higher decay (1.06 mV.h⁻¹), though still better than W-S SS. ICP-OES postmortem analysis revealed Fe leaching from the NiFe catalyst while no Ni dissolution was observed, indicating chemical stability of nickel in these operating conditions.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion we highlight the critical role of PTL thickness and interlayer materials and structure in determining the performance and durability of a flow field-free AEM water electrolyzer. The use of 450 μm thick Ni felt improved mass transport and mechanical resilience even under high external applied pressure of 20 bar. However, while adding secondary interlayers like Inconel and W-S SS enhanced initial performance, their long-term stability was limited by chemical passivation in oxidative alkaline condition of anode compartment. In contrast, replacing them with W-S Ni provided chemical durability and resulted in very low degradation rates (0.18 mV.h⁻¹). These findings highlight the importance of carefully balancing interlayer design, PTL thickness, and material selection to ensure both high initial performance and durability of an AEMWE over time.

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